

FIRST RECORD OF NUTMEG MANNIKIN
Lonchura punctulata (AVES:ESTRILDIDAE) FOR CUBA

YARODDY RODRÍGUEZ¹, ORLANDO H. GARRIDO², AND ARTURO KIRKCONNELL³
¹*Calle H entre 2 y 3 No.370, Reparto Lugones, Ciego de Ávila, Cuba;* ²*Calle 60 No. 1706 entre 17 y 19, Marianao 13, La Habana, Cuba;* and ³*Museo Nacional de Historia Natural de Cuba, Calle Obispo 61, Habana Vieja, Cuba*

THE FIRST RECORD of the Nutmeg Mannikin (*Lonchura punctulata*) for Cuba is an individual collected by Yaroddy Rodríguez on 6 March 2003 in the outskirts of the city of Ciego de Ávila. For several years before then, however, *Lonchura punctulata* was known in Cuba (Garrido 1997). Garrido (1997) had reported several flocks of this species in the province of Guantánamo (near Vilorio). Furthermore, some “pájareros” had captured and kept several individuals in captivity. This bird is locally known as “Damero,” because of its resemblance to a chessboard.

At present, we are aware of *Lonchura punctulata* only in the oriental provinces, but we do not doubt that the bird has dispersed to several other regions of Cuba; i.e., wherever they find a suitable habitat in rice and other plantations where running water is present.

Four specimens are deposited in the National Museum of Natural History of Cuba (MNHNC—Nos. 1668, 1669, 1670, 1671). Rodríguez captured the first bird from among a flock of *Lonchura malacca*, a species that has been increasing rapidly in numbers in several provinces of Cuba. In 2003, Pedro Cuadrado donated three birds that he had captured near Gibara, Holguín Province, and kept in captivity. Although *L. punctulata* is also widespread and increasing in numbers, its settlement in Cuba is more recent than *L. malacca*.

LITERATURE CITED

GARRIDO, O. H. 1997. *Sicalis flaveola* (Aves: Emberizidae)—nueva especie para la avifauna cubana. *Pitirre* 10:55.

RECENT SIGHTINGS OF WHITE-CROWNED PIGEON AND BLACK SWIFT ON NEVIS

JULIAN FRANCIS

65 Fleet Street, London EC4Y 1HS, England

Abstract.—White-crowned Pigeon (*Columba leucocephala*) and Black Swift (*Cypseloides niger*) were sighted on Nevis on 16 April 2003.

Key words: Black Swift, *Columba leucocephala*, *Cypseloides niger*, Nevis, White-crowned Pigeon

WHITE-CROWNED PIGEON (*Columba leucocephala*) and Black Swift (*Cypseloides niger*) are both mentioned in *The birds of Nevis* (Hilder 1989). White-crowned Pigeon is recorded as having been seen only once in February. No clear details are provided of the frequency or the time of year of sightings in relation to Black Swift. Raffaele *et al.* (1998) give ranges which would include Nevis for both these birds but no other specific details for Nevis. Accordingly, my sightings of both these birds on 16 April 2003 are of value. A White-crowned Pigeon was seen in a palm next to Nelson Spring (a

small lake just behind Pinneys Beach in northwestern Nevis). Three Black Swifts were seen flying east over Gingerland (a village in southwestern Nevis) in stormy weather.

LITERATURE CITED

HILDER, H. 1989. *The birds of Nevis*. Charlestown: Nevis Historical and Conservation Society.
RAFFAELE, H., J. WILEY, O. GARRIDO, A. KEITH, AND J. RAFFAELE. 1998. *A guide to the birds of the West Indies*. London: Helm.